

Volumetric Absorptive Microsampling and Conductive Vial Electromembrane Extraction for the Analysis of Pharmaceuticals in Whole Blood

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1. FIGURES

Figure S1: VAMS tips and commercially available conductive vial EME device.

Figure S2: Optimization of donor solvent composition in small conductive donor vials with 100 µL of 250 mM formic acid (a) and 250 mM formic acid with 12.5% methanol (b). Results are presented as a mean process efficiency ± SD.

Figure S3: **Optimization of applied voltage.** Comparison of 50 V used in generic B1 method (a) and 100 V (b). Results are presented as a mean process efficiency \pm SD.

RED PRINCIPLES (analytical performance)			R1: Scope of application		R2: LOD and LOQ			R3: Precision			R4: Accuracy		
	Method number	Method name	0-100	LOD	LOQ	0-100	RSD% (repeatability)	RSD% (reproducibility)	0-100	Relative error (%)	Recovery (%)	0-100	
	1	Electromembrane extraction	110	NA	1 ng/mL	100	1.6 - 13.3	NA	90	85.9 - 111.1	less relevant	96	
2	Conventional method	-	NA	NA	-	NA	NA	-	NA	NA	-		

GREEN PRINCIPLES (green chemistry)			G1: Toxicity of reagents (impact and biodegradation)			G2: Amount of reagents and waste			G3: Consumption of energy and other media		G4: Direct impacts (safety, use of animals and GMOs)		
	Method number	Method name	Total number of pictograms	0-100	Reagent consumption	Waste production	0-100	1-100	Occupational hazards	Safety of users (0-100)	Use of animals (0 if no, 1 if yes)	Use of GMO (0 if no, 1 if yes)	
	1	Electromembrane extraction	8	84	Correlate with Waste	5 mL/100 runs	95	95	2	96	0	0	
2	Conventional method	5	90	Correlate with Waste	20 mL/100 runs	80	95	1	98	0	0		

BLUE PRINCIPLES (practical side)			B1: Cost-efficiency		B2: Time-efficiency		B3: Requirements			B4: Operational simplicity		
	Method number	Method name	Total cost	0-100	Speed of analysis	0-100	Sample consumption	Sample consumption (0-100)	Other needs: advanced instruments, skills, facilities (0-100)	Miniaturization (0-100)	Integration and automation (0-100)	Portability (0-100)
	1	Electromembrane extraction	Very high	85	moderate	100	1 mL / 100 runs	100	90	100	100	0
2	Conventional method	Very high	85	moderate	100	1 mL / 100 runs	100	100	100	100	0	100

Figure S4: Evaluation of method's sustainability for selected analytes according to RGB 12 algorithm [1]. The scores were assigned based on the approach described in [2]. However, for the waste production parameter, only organic solvents were considered as waste, while water was excluded. This choice was made to better highlight the key differences between the methods and provide a more accurate reflection of their greenness. One mark was deducted from the score for every millilitre of waste. Analytical performance (red principle) was evaluated only for the electromembrane extraction method, as the necessary parameters were not determined for the conventional extraction.

2. TABLES

Compound	Retention time (min)	Precursor Ion (m/z)	Product Ion (m/z)	Collision energy (V)
Alprenolol	3.93	250.41	173.1	17
		250.41	116.1 (quantifier)	17
Amitriptyline	4.67	278.2	105	25
		278.2	91 (quantifier)	29
Bumetanide	6.04	365.1	240.1 (quantifier)	17
		365.1	184.1	25
Chlorpromazine	4.86	319.1	246	25
		319.1	214.1 (quantifier)	49
Chlorprothixene	4.93	316.1	271 (quantifier)	21
		316.1	231	33
Cinnarizine	5.5	369.51	167.1 (quantifier)	21
		369.51	152.1	50
Clomipramine	4.98	315.2	242.1	29
		315.2	227 (quantifier)	45
Clotrimazole	4.97	277	241.1	30
		277	165.1 (quantifier)	30
Cocaine	3.33	304.2	182.1 (quantifier)	21
		304.2	105	37
DBDAP*	4.62	264.2	219.2 (quantifier)	17
		264.2	203.2	33
Diltiazem	4.3	415.2	178 (quantifier)	25
		415.2	150.1	49
Doxepin	4.22	280.2	107 (quantifier)	25
		280.2	91	49
Droperidol	3.88	380.2	194.1 (quantifier)	13
		380.2	165.1	29
Fluoxetine	4.83	310.1	148.1 (quantifier)	5
Haloperidol	4.33	376.1	165.1 (quantifier)	25
		376.1	123	50
Hydroxyzine	4.61	375.2	201.1 (quantifier)	21
		375.2	166.1	50
Lidocaine	2.68	235.2	86.1 (quantifier)	17
Loperamide	5.24	478.11	267.2 (quantifier)	25
		478.11	210.1	50
Methadone	4.71	310.2	265.2 (quantifier)	13
		310.2	105	33
Mianserin	4.1	265.2	208.1 (quantifier)	21
		265.2	91	50
Nortriptyline	4.6	264.41	105	21
		264.41	91 (quantifier)	25
Noscapine	3.65	414.2	353.1	25
		414.2	220.1 (quantifier)	21
O-desmethylenlafaxine	2.87	264.2	246.2 (quantifier)	9
		264.2	107	41
Oxprenolol	3.52	266.2	225.1	13
		266.2	116.1 (quantifier)	17
Papaverine	3.59	340.41	324.1 (quantifier)	33
		340.41	202.1	29
Perphenazine	4.61	404.2	171.1 (quantifier)	25
		404.2	143.1	29
Pethidine	3.39	248.31	220.2 (quantifier)	21
		248.31	174.1	21
Pimozide	5.18	462.2	328.2 (quantifier)	33
		462.2	147.1	41
Prochlorperazine	4.72	374.1	141.2 (quantifier)	21
		374.1	113.1	33
Promazine	4.42	285.1	180.1	49
		285.1	86.1 (quantifier)	17

Promethazine	4.34	285.41	198	25
		285.41	86.1 (quantifier)	13
Propranolol	3.88	260.2	183.1	17
		260.2	116.1 (quantifier)	17
Pyrilamine	3.24	286.2	241.1	9
		286.2	121.1 (quantifier)	25
Quinine	2.72	163.1	189.1 (quantifier)	13
		163.1	117	41
Raloxifene	4.22	473.6	269	37
		473.6	112.1 (quantifier)	30
Reserpine	4.97	609.3	397.2	29
		609.3	195.1 (quantifier)	41
Thioridazine	5.2	371.2	258.1	29
		371.2	126.1 (quantifier)	25
Triclabendazole	6.89	358.9	343.9	29
		358.9	273.9 (quantifier)	41
Trimipramine	4.76	295.2	193.1	49
		295.2	100.1 (quantifier)	17
Venlafaxine	3.63	278.2	260.2 (quantifier)	9
		278.2	121.1	33
Verapamil	4.69	455.3	303.2	25
		455.3	165.1 (quantifier)	29

* DBDAP = 2,6-di-tert-butyl-4-(dimethylaminomethyl)phenol

Table S1: List of all pharmaceuticals determined by the assay with their LC-MS/MS detection parameters.

All analytes	log P	Linearity (R ²)	PE (%)	Precision (RSD %)		Accuracy (%)	
		1–1000	100	100	500	100	500
Oxprenolol	2.17	0.9963	7.1	16.3	31.1	83.1	97.4
O-desmethylvenlafaxine	2.27	0.8684	0.1	34.8	66.2	79.9	36.9
Cocaine	2.28	0.9989	37.0	7.2	18.8	80.8	94.9
Bumetanide	2.42	0.9771	1.3	10.6	6.8	91.9	77.6
Pethidine	2.46	0.9951	19.9	14.5	26.7	79.3	100.6
Quinine	2.51	0.8982	1.1	19.3	25.1	67.4	145.5
Noscapine	2.58	0.9976	48.4	2.7	7.1	95.7	105.0
Propranolol	2.58	0.9961	15.7	12.6	21.5	79.4	98.9
Alprenolol	2.69	0.9945	11.7	8.6	26.2	79.4	100.3
Diltiazem	2.73	0.9977	53.5	1.4	8.6	94.9	103.7
Venlafaxine	2.74	0.9964	21.3	12.7	31.8	80.7	97.4
Lidocaine	2.84	0.9925	5.9	10.6	33.6	81.7	101.0
Droperidol	3.01	0.9964	21.4	11.5	20.3	84.9	100.2
Pyrimidine	3.04	0.996	52.6	12.4	19.5	77.5	102.2
Papaverine	3.08	0.9988	58.0	11.4	7.1	93.6	103.5
Hydroxyzine	3.41	0.9279	46.2	18.4	11.2	87.5	144.3
Reserpine	3.53	0.9602	35.3	21.5	29.2	98.1	124.4
Haloperidol	3.66	0.9946	47.6	10.1	6.0	95.8	108.8
Perphenazine	3.69	0.1386	0.3	101.7	173.2	-224.5	359.1
Mianserin	3.83	0.9992	43.6	7.7	6.8	92.7	99.3
Doxepin	3.84	0.9993	45.3	4.4	7.9	85.9	99.3
Promazine	3.93	0.6165	4.3	47.7	122.9	8.3	172.0
Fluoxetine	4.17	0.9995	48.0	1.6	9.9	90.4	99.6
Promethazine	4.29	0.6007	4.3	49.0	122.5	4.1	175.0
Prochlorperazine	4.38	0.2264	0.3	91.4	144.5	-146.4	282.6
Nortriptyline	4.43	0.9933	42.8	7.6	13.3	87.0	111.1
Chlorpromazine	4.54	0.4424	1.1	110.0	116.5	-42.3	213.8
DBDAP*	4.60	0.9994	62.1	4.9	3.7	87.5	101.5
Trimipramine	4.76	0.9961	27.7	28.9	16.6	88.5	98.6
Loperamide	4.77	0.9976	65.8	5.0	9.3	97.3	107.9
Amitriptyline	4.81	0.9987	34.8	16.7	6.6	81.9	98.8
Clomipramine	4.88	0.9989	34.9	6.8	6.7	85.9	100.6
Methadone	5.01	0.9965	37.6	34.4	37.4	95.5	109.6
Verapamil	5.04	0.9992	54.3	25.3	11.9	95.8	104.0
Chlorprothixene	5.07	0.9984	21.9	17.5	10.9	83.5	96.9
Raloxifene	5.47	0.8628	7.0	11.6	54.3	69.1	137.0
Thioridazine	5.47	0.3643	0.3	103.6	119.3	-62.7	238.1
Pimozide	5.83	0.9994	40.2	33.8	10.2	97.0	103.4
Clotrimazole	5.84	0.9974	29.6	5.9	19.6	93.3	93.7
Cinnarizine	5.88	0.999	24.8	36.2	6.5	90.1	103.8
Triclabendazole	5.88	0.7757	0.0	70.1	38.9	82.6	18.0

* DBDAP = 2,6-di-tert-butyl-4-(dimethylaminomethyl)phenol

Table S2: **Results of evaluation experiments for all determined pharmaceuticals.** Linearity was verified within the concentration range of 1 – 1000 ng/mL using 6 concentration levels (n=3), process efficiency (PE) was tested at a concentration 100 ng/mL (n=4), precision and accuracy at two concentration levels – 100 ng/mL and 500 ng/mL (n=4). Log P values were obtained from [3].

Compound	PE (%)		Mean PE (%)
Papaverine	86	68	77
Noscapine	81	45	63
Mianserin	63	54	59
Doxepin	60	60	60
Diltiazem	68	56	62
Haloperidol	63	61	62
Nortriptyline	56	46	51
DBDAP*	35	27	31
Fluoxetine	52	67	60
Clomipramine	84	73	79
Loperamide	62	71	67

* DBDAP = 2,6-di-tert-butyl-4-(dimethylaminomethyl)phenol

Table S3: **Process efficiencies (PE) for selected analytes** evaluated using a conventional extraction method – direct ultrasound-assisted extraction with methanol from whole blood collected on VAMS tips. Verification performed at 100 ng/mL.

References:

- [1] P.M. Nowak, R. Wietecha-Posluszny, J. Pawliszyn, White Analytical Chemistry: An approach to reconcile the principles of Green Analytical Chemistry and functionality, *Trac-Trend Anal Chem* 138 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2021.116223>.
- [2] B. Jain, R. Jain, P.M. Nowak, N. Ali, M.N. Ansari, A. Kabir, L.P. Chandravanshi, S. Sharma, Comparison of various sample preparation methods for benzodiazepines in terms of the principles of white analytical chemistry, *Trac-Trend Anal Chem* 171 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2024.117524>.
- [3] <https://chemicalize.com>, ChemAxon, Budapest, Hungary.